

METHODS OF TRAINING GENERAL ENDURANCE IN FOOTBALL PLAYERS AGED 12-13 YEARS

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Abstract. This article is dedicated to training general endurance in football players aged 12-13 years in this article says how to learn playing football. It says how to learn rules of playing football. Why we need endurance in playing football during the game. How to keep general endurance in football players aged 12-13 years. It shows fitness drills and importance of endurance in football players during competition. It talks what physical exercises football players must do for training general endurance and strength. Today football places high demands on the motor, mental and technical abilities of players, who are to make optimal decisions in the context of rapidly changing game situations. The system of training young football players is undoubtedly the foundation for building the future sports reserve of the country. However, there are contradictions between the proposed methods and the objective of training football players in general.

Keywords: cardiovascular system, heart rate variability, regulatory adaptive status, young football players, physical training, competition, endurance, popular, health, adults, heart, tactics, fitness, running, jumping, quality, to win, important ability mental, football field exercise, team, activity, development to fight, friendship, to help, goal, football match to help, effect, skill, endurance, exercise, oxygen, body.

МЕТОДИКА ТРЕНИРОВКИ ОБЩЕЙ ВЫНОСЛИВОСТИ ФУТБОЛИСТОВ 12-13 ЛЕТ

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы методики воспитания общей терпеливости футболистов 12-13 лет. Указывается как надо учиться играть в футбол. Каким образом изучать правила игры в футбол. Почему нужно терпение на футбольной площадке во время игры. Как держать терпение футболистов 12-13 лет. Указываются упражнения ловкости и важность терпеливости во время соревнования. Говорится какие физические упражнения надо выполнять футболистам для воспитания терпеливости и ловкости. Сегодня футбол представляет высокие требования мотора умственное и технические таланты игроков в контексте частое изменения ситуации игры. Система подготовки молодых футболистов бесспорно. Основание для строения будущего источника страны. К статье имеется уравнение среди прошлой методики и предмет общее подготовки молодых футболистов.

Ключевые слова: сердечно-сосудистая система изменение темп сердце, регулировка статус сокращение молодые футболисты, физическое воспитание, соревнование, терпеливость, популярный, здоровое, подростки, сердце, тактика, ловкость, бег, прыжок, качества, победить важное талант умственные футбольное упражнения, команда, активность, развитие бороться, дружба помогать, гол, футбольный матч, влияние квалификация, терпеливость упражнение, кислород, тело.

INTRODUCTION

This study employed the following methods: a theoretical analysis and synthesis of scientific and methodological literature on the research topic, a pedagogical experiment,

registration of competitive activity, and methods of mathematical statistics. The experiment involved twenty 12-13-year-old football players.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

An analysis of the studies conducted in this field has revealed that the game-based training principles coincide with the modern view on football development and its trends in the world. An algorithm is proposed to compile game-based exercises from simple to complex ones using the example of the beginning and development of an attack in zone of defense. The indices of technical and tactical skills are introduced.

Football is the most popular and, as well, the most popular means of physical development of the population, strengthening its health. This is a really popular game for adults, teenagers and children. At the heart of a football match is a struggle between two teams that unite players to achieve a common goal - the desire to win. The drive to win teaches players to act as a team, to help each other, and to develop a sense of friendship and camaraderie.

Playing football can be a great way to improve your overall fitness.

A person's endurance when performing an exercise is his or her ability to work for a long time without slowing down the pace of work. Endurance depends on the body's functional reserves, the level of physical fitness, the important conditions under which the work is performed. Regular exercise increases the body's resistance to these activities. Endurance is the body's ability to fight fatigue, which develops when the body engages in physical activity, which leads to a decrease in its ability to work. With increasing endurance, the duration of maintaining a high level of working capacity in the body is prolonged. Endurance is divided into several types: general endurance, special endurance, resistance to dynamic work, resistance to static stress.

RESULTS

When it comes to preseason football training, the first thing that comes to mind for athletes is jogging to nausea. Under this plan, the first week of football training is designed to bring the athletes back to training mode after a few weeks of vacation. Balanced cardio loads will not be stressful for the body if interval sprints are started from the very beginning, but will serve as a good base for aerobic preparation before the subsequent exercises. This week's other two football training drills should be anything but uniform cardio, to improve muscle and cardiovascular mobility, without a monotonous load like running.

Session 1: 45 minute run. Must work up a little sweat, average heart rate. Focus on 70% of your maximum heart rate.

Session 2 and 3: General sports exercises, maybe swimming, cycling (in-door cycling), rowing machines, etc.

DISCUSSION

Football fitness training before the competition includes a mixture of sprints at different distances with a change of direction. These exercises will prepare the body for playing situations on the field. In this case, you should try to do exercises of high quality: be mobile, make quick turns, accelerate powerfully.

Session 1. Shackle Running.

Sprint from the goal line to the goalkeeper line, then back on foot. Then a sprint from the goal line to the penalty mark, then you walk back on foot. Sprint from the goal line to the half-way line, then walk back. Repeat this cycle 6 to 8 times depending on fatigue.

As a child grows and develops, the content of games also changes: if play activities are of a simple nature in the early stages, then they become richer. P.F. Lesgaft describes games as a means of physical education in his exercise system. She focuses on preparing the child for life through play. His demands for action games have not lost their value to this day. For example, he should set clear goals for each game, match the strengths and abilities of the participants, have a positive impact on the player, conduct them systematically and regularly, engage students, had stressed the need to try to increase its independence.

Power development games. In doing so, the teacher should choose games that have a positive effect on the development of the desired muscle groups. In strengthbuilding games, the student overcomes his or her own body weight, any external weight, or an opponent's weight (resistance). The following games are recommended to develop strength: —Rooster-rooster game, —Capricorn, —Overturn from the horse, —Lame wolf and sheep, —Drop into the pit. For example, the more children in the game "Rooster-rooster", the more interesting the game will be. This game is mainly played by boys. The children play in pairs. On both sides, group leaders are elected. The teacher divides the class into two teams. They look at each other face to face. There will be one student from each of the two teams. They hold their hands behind their backs, jump on one leg, and begin to push each other with their shoulders. In this case, no child can put his foot on the ground first or play with his hand behind his back. The main purpose of the game is to test the strength of students, to increase endurance

General endurance and general fitness started with general ability to resist fatigue during physical activity but without any significant influence on sports performance. It is very useful for leisure sport activities, for non-elite athletes to maintain basic fitness or functional and energy systems. General endurance and general fitness on a good level is the basis for athletes to achieve better recovery, increase volume and intensity of training process or higher frequency of training stimuli etc. This type of general fitness and general endurance can be improved with various cyclic movements such as walking, running, cycling, canoing, sculling or working out on specific fitness machines.

Physical education. This game was widely used by our ancestors in ancient times. Endurance games. In many national folk movement games, physical qualities such as speed and endurance are nurtured as a result of extremely fast-paced exercises. In such games, the physical load (load) is also gradually increased. For example, enlarging the area; reducing the number of players without reducing the area; increase the number of play equipment (sticks, handkerchiefs, skullcaps, coats, balls, etc.) to extend the running distance; increase the number of obstacles; applying complex exercises and increasing their number, and so on.

Games such as "Knife under the knee", "Throwing a stick in a circle", "Jumping over an obstacle", "Stone game" are recommended to develop flexibility. are given. For example, we recommend the —Stone Game game for 11-12 year olds, which is fun and effectively enhances the quality of flexibility. The participants in the game stand in a circle. Each of them, except for one player, holds five stones in his hands. Rule of the game: At the first signal from the teacher, players throw their stones in front of them and turn their backs to the center of the circle. According to the second signal, they turn sharply to the first position and each player tries to get his stone. The player who does not have time to remove the stone is considered the loser and the game starts again. The winner is the player who is the most agile, agile and fast-moving, who gets his stone on time.

In the game, students are divided into two groups. A distance of 30 meters should be marked with two dummies. Two children from both groups should run the same distance and complete the game — the dummy should not fall off the head. The game continues until all the children in the group have a skullcap on their head. The team that fulfills the condition the fastest is the winner.

Throughout the game, when they have the ball, each team has to do a lot of attacking moves using different means and methods of fighting. Therefore, the most important thing in tactics is to know the specific means of attack and defense, the methodology and the widespread use of their capabilities in the attack, which will ensure the achievement of the goal - all this characterizes the tactical maturity of individual athletes. generally.

The essence of a football player's tactics is to be able to effectively use his abilities (physical, technical, mental) and to effectively use the methods of carrying the ball, which helps to overcome the opponent's resistance in a very short time. Tactics are one of the most powerful and important components of modern football. Tactics slowly but surely began to influence the development of the game of football without deviations and became a leader among other components. Tactics are not only changing the face of modern football, but also profoundly influencing the form, means and methods of training.

Different running with a change of direction, different types of jumps, different body movements in structure, kicks, passes, stopping and carrying the ball, moving with maximum speed, developing willpower, tactical thinking - allows you to consider football as a sport that develops many important qualities, necessary for an athlete of any specialty. In football, the emotional properties of ball control technique make it possible to use it as a means of active recreation. In football, as in other sports, there are two teams that want to win. The fight for victory requires athletes to have very strong physical, mental and strength qualities.

In the stages of training and improving the skills of young football players, the usual methods of physical education are used: exercises, games, competitions, demonstrations, oral speech, error correction. All methods are used in close connection with each other. However, the percentage of their use depends on many factors: the stage and objectives of training, the age and individual characteristics of the participants, their level of training. In today's football, the technical-tactical system is the organization of team play based on the individual characteristics of each player, correctly placed on the football field.

The practical tactical elements of a football game are: - appropriate way of combining and oscillating players' offensive and defensive movements based on the opponent's actions and game logic: - the method of orderly distribution of power during the game: - psychological influence on the opponent is a way to disguise the real possibilities. In modern football, the process of training in technical techniques and competitive tactics continues at all stages of long-term training.

Anaerobic endurance training in football

Anaerobic endurance is generally trained in repeated sprint setting. Heavily debated content within repeated sprint training are:

Work to rest ratio (1, 38, 51, 52)

Active vs. passive recovery (57)

Training intervention was 6 (17) or 10 (64) weeks with a training frequency of 1 (64), 2-3 (17) training sessions/week and a work to rest ratio of 1:4 - 1:6 for sprints of 30-80 m in length (17, 64).

Improvements were seen in 40 meter sprint time (64), repeated sprint performance (64), VO₂max and also a proportional increase in type II muscle fiber type (17).

With regard to youth, training seemed to be successfully implemented after peak height velocity (PHV). Generally repeated sprint ability seemed to develop with age, training (11), however physiological foundations are developed during/after puberty, as the results in repeated sprinting in different age groups were less variable from age 15-18 (49, 58) and differences with between age groups disappeared after controlling for age at peak height velocity (45).

However, we believe that anaerobic endurance can also be trained in a “better” football specific setting.

CONCLUSIONS

The research has theoretically justified and experimentally proved the effectiveness of the game-based method as the basic principle of training the 12-13-year-old football players.

At the age of 12 years young football players had a burst of vagal activity (HF-waves) and a favorable autonomic balance was established at rest with the significant predominance of parasympathetic effects (HF-waves) over the sympathetic ones (LF-waves) on the background of a slight introduction of suprasegmental regulation mechanisms (VLF-waves) of heart rate. The data obtained prove that the age of 12 is a nodical period for young football players in formation of the mechanisms of the parasympathetic regulation of cardiovascular system.

Obviously, the ultimate goal of any sports pre-season training, or football training as its part, is to improve athletic performance to the maximum potential. There are many ways to accelerate the progress of players, but the most popular remains participation in special football camps or training in professional football academies.

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